

JOURNAL ON COMMUNICATIONS

ISSN:1000-436X

REGISTERED

Scopus[®]

www.jocs.review

Multiple Regression Analysis of the School of Teacher Education Students' Performance in Technology for Teaching and Learning

Janet D. Barrera

*J.H. Cerilles State College, School of Teacher Education
Dumingag, Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines, 7023*

Abstract: *This multiple regression analysis research pursued to examine if online learning engagement, teacher-student relationship, teacher's facilitation skills, self-regulated learning, digital literacy, and conceptual understanding in ICT policies and issues and delivering technology-enhanced lessons predict the academic performance of the students in Technology for Teaching and Learning. This was quantitative research which specifically used descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive analysis of the data was done with the frequency and percentage distribution, weighted arithmetic mean and standard deviation. The study involved a total of 227 students from the BEd, BPEd, BSEd English and Mathematics. The questionnaire-checklist was adapted: the online learning engagement from M. Dixon [15]; teacher-student relationship from Wanders et al. [16]; teachers' facilitation skills from Zimmerman and Kulokowich [17]; self-regulated learning from Lan, Barnard, Stevens & Mullen [18] and Bernard, Paton & Lan [19]; and the digital literacy scale from Mutlu et al [20]. The student-participants have very high level of online learning engagement and teacher-student relationship; high level of self-regulated learning and digital literacy skills. The students disclosed that their teachers had very good facilitation skills. The teachers' facilitation skills, self-regulated learning and the students' digital learning skills were the found to predict the students' performance in Technology for Teaching and Learning.*

Keywords: *Multiple Regression Analysis, School of Teacher Education, Students, Performance, Technology for Teaching and Learning*

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology is essential to teaching and learning, especially in programs that train teachers to meet the needs of the modern classroom. It also improves student engagement and personalizes learning experiences. The use of technology in education includes a wide range of instruments and materials that facilitate and improve educational processes. Learning environments that are interactive and engaging have replaced traditional education thanks to innovations like interactive whiteboards, laptops, tablets, mobile applications, and online platforms. These tools make it easier to access a multitude of materials and knowledge that enhance learning and accommodate a range of learning preferences.

Teachers can design engaging, customized lessons that address each student's requirements and foster a deeper comprehension of difficult subjects by incorporating technology into the classroom. Digital tools also make it possible for students to work together on projects that transcend geographical borders, which promotes community and shared learning.

Understanding and exploiting technology is crucial in teacher education programs to give aspiring educators the tools they need to succeed in the current digital era. It is essential that teacher candidates master the use of instructional resources as technology advances. In order to ensure that teachers can adequately educate their students for a future driven by technology, this proficiency comprises the capacity to effectively browse, choose, and apply technology in their teaching practices.

Students' active engagement in their education is increasingly seen as a sign of effective classroom instruction and valued. But lack of interest in some topics, like STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics), worries experts and lawmakers. For instance, the Horizon 2020 Work Program of the European Commission [14] highlights the importance of science education more effectively enlist youth in science education. Similarly, research conducted in Australia found a persistent reduction in high school students' interest in and participation in science and math classes. Enhancing students' involvement and enthusiasm in STEM topics is a passionate goal shared by educators and stakeholders. This is pertinent to online education because it is widespread in numerous professions. In the interim, it's crucial to examine earlier research on students' participation, which will offer helpful details on practical application. Numerous studies have been conducted on engagement, particularly those examining the causes and consequences of involvement in traditional classroom settings. Achievement and dropping out are two examples of these consequences of involvement [1; 2]; another is problem-solving abilities [3]. Hence, the students' engagement could relate to their academic performance.

According to Xu et al. [4], behavioral engagement is the degree of student participation, which includes attendance, assignment submission, and discussion participation. Since higher behavioral engagement shows that students are actively participating in their education, it is frequently associated with higher academic performance. Improved learning outcomes, for instance, are favorably connected with regular involvement in online forums and timely completion of tasks [5].

Poor academic performance can be attributed to students who feel they have a bad relationship with their professors, depend more on them, have difficult lives, and have few personal ties [6]. The performance of both sides is greatly impacted by the teacher-student connection. The degree of student achievement and the success of teachers' jobs are both impacted by this relationship when it comes to managing issues in the classroom. Vlachopoulos and Makri [7] assert that education is a highly interactive process whose efficacy is dependent on the methods used. The relationship between teachers and students is crucial in the context of education. Stated differently, the process of teaching and learning depends on this contact. Furthermore, positive relationships between teachers and students are linked to higher levels of motivation, engagement, and academic success; on the other hand, negative relationships can result in lower levels of motivation, disengagement, and subpar academic performance [8].

1.2 Objectives

The study endeavors to conduct a multiple regression analysis of the school of teacher education students' performance in Technology for Teaching and Learning during the second semester of the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study dealt with the level of online learning engagement of the participants; teacher-student relationship, teacher's facilitation skills, self-regulated learning, digital literacy, and conceptual understanding in ICT policies and issues and delivering technology-enhanced lessons; academic performance of the students in Technology for Teaching and Learning; and the test for significant relationship between the predictor variables and the students' academic performance in TTL.

1.3 Research Methodology

This was quantitative research which specifically used descriptive-correlational design. The study involved a total of 227 students from the BEd, BPed, BSEd English and Mathematics. Descriptive analysis of the data was done with the frequency and percentage distribution, and weighted arithmetic mean; and multiple regression analysis research.

The questionnaire-checklist was adapted: the online learning engagement from Dixon [15]; teacher-student relationship from Wanders et al. [16]; teachers' facilitation skills from Zimmerman and Kulokowich [17]; self-regulated learning from Lan, Bremer, Stevens & Mullen [18] and Bernard, Paton & Lan [19]; and the digital literacy scale from Mutlu et al [20].

2.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 depicts the online learning environment of the participants. It can be noted that all groups of participants yielded very satisfactory level of online learning environment. This suggests that the students experienced satisfaction and contentment with their online learning experiences. They described their online learning platforms and activities as simple and easy for them to use which encouraged more engagement in learning activities and more accessible without being overwhelmed. The online learning environment allowed conversations, group projects, and utilized multimedia materials which are vital for sustaining students' attention and engagement in the educational process. Furthermore, the good teaching strategies, organized classes and timely feedback from teachers were favorable in the learning process [9].

Table 1. Online Learning Environment of the Participants

Programs/Sections	WAM	Interpretation
BPEd 1A	4.35	Very Satisfactory
BPEd 1B	4.46	Very Satisfactory
BEED	4.53	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1A	4.37	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1B	4.38	Very Satisfactory
BS Math	4.24	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.39	Very Satisfactory

A good, caring, and positive connection between students and instructors that is marked by respect, concern, and support for one another manifest a satisfactory level of student-teacher interactions. In this instance, the instructor creates a supportive atmosphere that puts the needs of each individual student first and encourages both their intellectual and emotional development [21]. In Table 2, the student-teacher relationships between the participants and their teachers are displayed.

According to the findings, it is important that teachers and students respect one another, foster an atmosphere of trust in which students feel free to express their ideas and emotions, demonstrate real concern for each student by attending to their specific needs, and promote effective communication. According to Coristine et al. [21], students who have a good rapport with their professors typically achieve better academically because they feel encouraged and secure in their ability to study.

Table 2. Student-Teacher Relationships Between the Participants and Their Teachers

Programs/Sections	WAM	Interpretation
BPEd 1A	4.25	Very Satisfactory
BPEd 1B	4.37	Very Satisfactory
BEED	4.34	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1A	4.11	Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1B	4.07	Satisfactory
BS Math	4.01	Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.19	Satisfactory

The facilitation skills of the teachers were considered by the participants as generally very satisfactory. This is shown in the overall mean of 4.42, interpreted as “very satisfactory.” Table 3 elucidates the responses of the students from the different programs and sections. This denotes that most of the teachers have what it takes to effectively direct and assist students’ learning in a group-based, interactive setting. Most of the teachers were adept at handling group dynamics and building bonds that facilitate cooperative learning, employ a variety of strategies to maintain student interest while accommodating varying learning preferences. Moisa [22] emphasized that teachers need to have strong facilitation skills to foster a positive learning environment where students are motivated to participate and engage.

Table 3. Participants’ Perceptions of the Facilitation Skills of the Teachers

Programs/Sections	WAM	Interpretation
BPEd 1A	4.50	Very Satisfactory
BPEd 1B	4.46	Very Satisfactory
BEED	4.57	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1A	4.45	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1B	4.27	Very Satisfactory
BS Math	4.24	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.42	Very Satisfactory

One essential ability that allows students to participate actively and purposefully in their education is self-regulated learning, or SRL. Students can organize, monitor, and assess their learning with the use of a variety of cognitive and metacognitive tools. Pupils that exhibit high levels of self-regulated learning actively participate in their education and are aware of the tactics that suit them best in various situations [123].

Academic achievement is associated with the capacity to self-regulate learning because it promotes independence and the perseverance needed to take on challenging assignments [24]. Pupils who successfully apply self-regulation techniques typically have higher levels of engagement with their coursework, exhibit superior time management skills, and maintain motivation under trying circumstances.

Table 4 manifests that the level of self-regulated learning of the students were generally very high as indicated by the overall mean of 4.24. Although, it can be noticed that the BPEd, BEEd and BSEd English students expressed very high level of self-regulated learning. On the other hand, most of the BSEd Math students registered high level along with some BSEd English students. These students were skilled at establishing objectives and creating plans of action to reach them; they evaluate their performance frequently and adjust

their plans of action to enhance their academic performance; and they routinely consider their learning experiences and make choices about how to change their behavior for better outcomes [24].

Table 4. Level of Self-Regulated Learning of the Participants

Programs/Sections	WAM	Interpretation
BPEd 1A	4.21	Very High
BPEd 1B	4.44	Very High
BEED	4.45	Very High
BSEd Engl 1A	4.23	Very High
BSEd Engl 1B	4.08	High
BS Math	4.11	High
Overall Mean	4.24	Very High

It can be observed from Table 5 that most of the participants perceived themselves to have very satisfactory level of digital literacy skills. This is evident in the overall mean of 4.23 which is interpreted as “very satisfactory.”

In Teacher Education Programs, a “very satisfactory level of digital literacy skills” denotes students’ ability to use digital tools and technologies to improve their teaching and learning processes. This involves having a firm grasp of how to use digital platforms for information creation, evaluation, and communication.

The findings indicate that the students could efficiently use digital environments to locate the information and resources needed for both teaching and learning [25]; evaluate the reliability of sources, distinguish between trustworthy and untrustworthy information, and make judgments based on digital content [26]; employ a variety of digital channels (such as social media, email, and video conferencing) to respectfully and clearly communicate ideas; exhibit competency in managing, creating, and manipulating information using technology while upholding ethical standards [26]; and recognize the significance of online safety and how to safeguard personal information from online threats [25].

Table 5. Digital Literacy Skills of the Participants

Programs/Sections	WAM	Interpretation
BPEd 1A	4.26	Very Satisfactory
BPEd 1B	4.37	Very Satisfactory
BEED	4.37	Very Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1A	4.19	Satisfactory
BSEd Engl 1B	4.21	Very Satisfactory
BS Math	3.96	Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.23	Very Satisfactory

It is disclosed in Table 6 that the majority of the students had satisfactory level of conceptual understanding of ICT policies and issues. This indicates that students demonstrate a sufficient degree of conceptual understanding of ICT policies and concerns are able to demonstrate that they have a comprehensive awareness of the goals, principles, and implications of information and communication technology (ICT) in educational settings. This

includes being able to understand how ICT may be used to enhance learning and the potential effects that legislation may have on teaching methods.

Table 6. Conceptual Understanding of the Participants on ICT Policies and Issues

Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory	31	13.66
Satisfactory	140	61.67
Average	45	19.82
Poor	11	4.85
Very Poor	0	0
Total	227	100.00

It is unfolded in Table 7 that most of the students have satisfactory level of academic performance in the Technology for Teaching and Learning subject. Out of 227 students, 207 or 91.19 percent had satisfactory performance level. This suggests that most of the students satisfactorily use technology to supplement their education and meet or surpass academic standards and produce desired results and use digital tools and resources to improve their teaching methods. According to the article “How Important is Technology in Education?” [10], the goal of using technology into instruction is to create a more conducive learning environment. Research indicates that interactive learning makes a substantial impact on students’ academic achievement, academic happiness, and overall well-being. Using digital learning resources in the classroom can boost student participation, assist teachers in creating more effective lesson plans, and eventually support improved student performance results.

Table 7. Academic Performance of the Participants in Technology for Teaching and Learning

Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory	3	1.32
Satisfactory	207	91.19
Average	17	7.49
Poor	0	0
Very Poor	0	0
Total	227	100.00

Table 8. Correlation Matrix of the Predictor Variables and Academic Performance of the Students in TTL

Variables	Correlation Coefficients	p-value	Decisions
• Online Learning Environment	0.153	0.021	S
• Teacher-Student Relationship	0.032	0.630	NS
• Teacher’s Facilitation Skills	0.135	0.042	S
• Self-Regulated Learning	0.112	0.091	NS
• Digital Literacy	0.070	0.295	NS
• Conceptual Understanding of ICT Policies and Issues Online Learning Environment	0.346	0.001	S

The correlation matrix shown in Table 8 indicates that the online learning environment, teacher’s facilitation skills and students’ conceptual understanding of ICT

policies and issues were significantly related to their academic performance in the Technology for Teaching and Learning subject.

Multiple Regression Model

Table 9. Model Coefficients

Predictors	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	59.14	3.4666	17.060	<0.001
A	-0.256	0.2141	-1.196	0.233
B	0.349	1.1462	0.304	0.761
C	-2.618	1.0185	-2.571	0.011
D	2.010	1.0036	2.003	0.046
E	1.647	1.0504	1.568	0.118
F	-1 .449	0.9243	-1.567	0.119
G	0.162	0.0341	4.745	<0.001

Improved student outcomes are correlated with instructors' facilitation skills, according to research. More improvements are observed in students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills in classrooms with knowledgeable facilitators. Better academic achievement results from fostering a learning atmosphere where students feel comfortable voicing their opinions and participating in deep conversations, which is enhanced by facilitation [11].

An online learning environment consists of all digital platforms and tools that are used for teaching. Studies reveal that incorporating information and communication technology (ICT) into educational environments improves students' academic performance and learning process [12; 13]. Online frameworks in particular offer variable resource accessibility, supporting a range of student learning preferences and methods. It has been demonstrated that these settings enhance student-teacher contact and communication, two essential components of successful learning [11].

3. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The student-participants have very high level of online learning engagement and teacher-student relationship; high level of self-regulated learning and digital literacy skills. The students disclosed that their teachers had very good facilitation skills.

The study found that students found online learning environments satisfactory, with simple platforms and activities encouraging engagement. Teachers and students should respect each other, foster trust, and promote effective communication. Teachers should handle group dynamics, maintain student interest, and employ various strategies to accommodate varying learning preferences.

Students generally demonstrated high self-regulated learning, satisfactory digital literacy skills, and a comprehensive understanding of ICT policies and concerns. They demonstrated a satisfactory level of academic performance in the Technology for Teaching and Learning subject. Factors such as online learning environment, teacher facilitation skills, and students' conceptual understanding of ICT policies significantly influenced their performance.

Teachers to utilize simple but more engaging online learning platforms and activities, encourage respect, trust, accountability and responsibility in the use of digital tools and technology, and consider the differentiated learning needs and preferences of students. The

curriculum to enhance by emphasizing the development of the students' self-regulated learning and promotion of the 21st century skills.

Acknowledgements

The researcher is grateful to the support, assistance and encouragement from Dr. Moises Glenn G. Tangalin, the Campus Director; Mr. Ruel S. Lasagas, the Research Director; Dr. Jerry B. Superales, Vice President for Research Extension and Resource Generation; and Dr. Edgardo H. Rosales, SUC President II.

REFERENCES

4.1 Journal Article

- [1] Steele, John P.; Fullagar, Clive. (2009). "Facilitators and outcomes of student engagement in a college setting." *The Journal of Psychology*, 143(1):5-27, doi:10.3200/JRLP.143.1.5-27.
- [2] Wang, M., & Fredricks, J. A. (2013). The Reciprocal Links Between School Engagement, Youth Problem Behaviors, and School Dropout During Adolescence. *Child Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12138>.
- [3] Eseryel, D.; Law, V.; Ifenthaler, D; Ge, X.; and Miller, R. (2014) "An investigation of the interrelationships between motivation, engagement, and complex problem solving in game-based learning." *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.* 17, 42-53.
- [4] Xu, X; Shi, Z; Bos, N; Wu, H. (2023) "Student engagement and learning outcomes: an empirical study applying a four-dimensional framework" *Medical Education Online*, Vol 28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2023.2268347>
- [5] Du, Z., Wang, F., Wang, S., & Xiao, X. (2022). Enhancing Learner Participation in Online Discussion Forums in Massive Open Online Courses: The Role of Mandatory Participation. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.819640>
- [6] Means & Pynes (2017) "Finding my way: perceptions of institutional support and belonging in low-income, first- generation, first-year college students." *Journal of College Student Development*.
- [7] Vlachopoulos, D. & Makri, A. (2019). "Online communication and interaction in distance higher education: a framework study of good practice." *International Review of Education*. DOI: [10.1007/s11159-019-09792-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-019-09792-3)
- [8] Shaukat, K. & Iqbal, F. (2020). "The impact of artificial intelligence and robotics on the future employment opportunities." *Trends in Computer Science and Information*. 5(1):050-054. DOI: [10.17352/tcsit.000022](https://doi.org/10.17352/tcsit.000022).
- [9] Elshami, W., Taha, M. H., Abuzaid, M., Saravanan, C., Al Kawas, S., & Abdalla, M. E. (2021). Satisfaction with online learning in the new normal: perspective of students

and faculty at medical and health sciences colleges. *Medical Education Online*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2021.1920090>.

- [10] *How Important Is Technology in Education? | American University*. (2024). School of Education Online. <https://soeonline.american.edu/technology-in-education/>.
- [11] Perez, Helina Jean; & Maimad, Felip Elizar D. (2023). Analysis on Teachers' Facilitation Skills and Students' Academic Performance in Core Learning Areas Under K-12 Framework. *E-Prosiding Persidangan Antarabangsa Sains Sosial & Kemanusiaan kali ke-8 (PASAK8 2023)*10 -11 Mei 2023 (e-ISSN: 2811-4051).
- [12] Mensah, R. O., Quansah, C., Oteng, B., & Nii Akai Netey, J. (2023). Assessing the effect of information and communication technology usage on high school student's academic performance in a developing country. *Cogent Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2023.2188809>.
- [13] Timotheou, S., Miliou, O., Dimitriadis, Y., Sobrino, S. V., Giannoutsou, N., Cachia, R., Monés, A. M., & Ioannou, A. (2022). Impacts of digital technologies on education and factors influencing schools' digital capacity and transformation: A literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11431-8>

4.2 Book

- [14] European Commission. (2016). EN Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2016 - 2017.

4.3 Chapter in a Book

- [15] Dixson, Marcia D. (2015) "Measuring student engagement in the online course: the online student engagement scale (OSE)." *Online Learning* Vol 19 Issue 4.
- [16] Wanders, Frank; Dijkstra, Anne Bert; Maslowski, Ralf; and der Veen, Ineke van. (2020). "The effect of teacher-student and student-student relationships on the societal involvement of students." *Research and Evaluation of Educational Effectiveness*.
- [17] Zimmerman, Whitney Alicia; Kulikowich, Joanna M. (2016). "Online learning self-efficacy in students with and without online learning experience." *American Journal of Distance Education*, v30 n3 p180-191.
- [18] Barnard, Lucy; Lan, William Y; Yen M. (2008). "Measuring self-regulation in online and blended learning environments." *The Internet and Higher Education*, Volume 12, Issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2008.10.005>
- [19] Barnard-Brak, Lucy; Lan, William Y. and Paton, Valerie Osland. (2010). "Profiles in self-regulated learning in an online learning environment." *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning* Volume 11, Number 1.
- [20] Mutlu, Tahsin; Gunes, Erhan and Bahcivan, Eralp. (2017). "Turkish adaptation of digital literacy scale and investigating pre-service science teachers' digital literacy.

- [21] Cristine, S., Russo, S., Fitzmorris, R., Beninato, P., & Rivolta, G. (2022). The importance of student-teacher relationships. Classroom practice in 2022.
- [22] Moiso, Deborah Rim (2024). *Teacher as facilitator: how to improve your lessons with facilitation* / SessionLab. SessionLab. <https://www.sessionlab.com/teacher-as-facilitator/>
- [23] Wolters, C. A., Iaconelli, R., Peri, J., Hensley, L. C., & Kim, M. (2023). Improving self-regulated learning and academic engagement: Evaluating a college learning to learn course. *Learning and Individual Differences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2023.102282>.
- [24] Toro, Stephanie. (2021). *How to Guide Students to Self-Regulated Learning*. George Lucas Educational Foundation. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/how-guide-students-self-regulated-learning/>.
- [25] Gripp, Moritz. (2023). *What is Digital Literacy and its Role in Education? — Futurize*. Futurize. <https://www.futurize.studio/what-is-digital-literacy-and-its-role-in-education>.
- [26] Jackman, David. (2024). *The Crucial Role of Digital Literacy in Shaping Tomorrow's Students - ICDL Global*. ICDL Global. <https://icdl.org/the-crucial-role-of-digital-literacy-in-shaping-tomorrows-students/>.